

of the keto form); 7.20 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.45 and 7.90 (10H, m, $2C_6H_8$).

Tetra-O-methyl, 6-6"-bischrysin (4): To a solution of the bis- β -diketone (6; 600 mg) in glacial acetic acid (20.0 ml) was added freshly fused sodium acetate (2.5 g) and the contents were heated on an oil bath for 4 h at 150-160°. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water. A precipitate obtained was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol as light yellow needles, 4 (300 mg), m.p. 254°. It was identical with the sample obtained above through bischalcone.

Selective demethylation of 4 to 7: Bischrysin tetramethyl ether (4; 1.0 g) was dissolved in dry CH_2Cl_2 (45.0 ml) and anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (600 mg) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a heating mantle for 30 h. The contents were then cooled to room temperature and diluted with water (500 ml). Dilute HCl (1:1) was added to acidify it. The solution was warmed on a water bath for 1 h and a yellow solid obtained was filtered, washed and dried. On crystallisation from methanol it gave bischrysin dimethyl ether, 7 (500 mg), m.p. 234°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; δ (with one drop of TFA) 4.0 (6H, s, 2-OCH₃), 6.50 (2H, s, I-8, II-8), 7.0 (2H, s, I-3, II-3), 7.5 and 7.95 (10H, m, $2C_6H_8$).

Methylation of dimethyl bischrysin 7 to 4: The dimethyl bischrysin (7; 100 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (50.0 ml), and dimethyl sulphate (1.0 ml) and fused K_2CO_3 (4.0 g) were added to it. The contents were refluxed for 30 h under anhydrous conditions and then worked up to give a compound, m.p. 254°, which was identical in all respects with 4.

Ditosylate 8: The dimethyl bischrysin (7; 200 mg) was dissolved in dry acetone (80.0 ml), and freshly crystallised tosyl chloride (220 mg) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1.0 g) were added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 40 h and then after cooling to room temperature the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. To the residue was added cold water when a precipitate was obtained. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from methanol as silky needles, 8 (100 mg), m.p. 246°. It did not give any colour with ferric chloride. Nmr could not be recorded due to solubility reasons.

Raney nickel reduction of 8: The ditosylate (8; 360 mg) was dissolved in dioxane (20.0 ml) and freshly prepared Raney nickel catalyst (360 mg) was added to it while stirring. Purified hydrogen gas was bubbled through the solution rapidly in the initial stages and later as a steady stream for 10 h. After completion of the reaction the catalyst was filtered off and dioxane was removed from the filtrate by distilling under reduced pressure. The residue was crystallised from methanol to give a light yellow compound (30 mg), m.p. 220-25°; gave a green colour with ferric chloride; tlc examination showed it to be a mixture of two compounds;

under uv light one spot showed a dull brown fluorescence and the other a blue fluorescence; δ 3.85 (6H, s, —OCH₃ of 7), 3.95 (6H, s, —OCH₃ of 9), 6.35 (2H, s, I-8, II-8 of 7), 6.40 (2H, s, I-8, II-8 of 9), 6.65 (2H, s, I-8, II-3 of 9), 6.70 (2H, s, I-3 II-3 of 7), 7.45, 7.85 (m, $2C_6H_8$ of both 7 and 9 and I-5, II-5 of 9).

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Chemical Investigation of *Bauhinia vahlii* Linn. (Leguminosae)

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A survey of literature revealed the presence of monoflavonoids and their glycosides in different species of *Bauhinia*¹⁻³. Since no work appeared to have been done on *Bauhinia vahlii* so far, this was subjected to systematic investigations.

Leaves of *Bauhinia vahlii* were found to contain betulinic acid, campesterol, stigmasterol, β -sitos-terol, quercetin, quercetin-3-glucoside, kaempferol, agathisflavone and its derivatives. The presence of biflavonoids is being reported here for the first time in *Bauhinia* species.

Experimental

The dried and powdered leaves (2 kg) were extracted with acetone. The total acetone extract was concentrated and passed through silica-gel column. The column was eluted with solvents of increasing polarity: petrol, benzene-ethyl acetate (9:1, 8:2, 7:3, 1:1), ethyl acetate and acetone. The benzene and benzene-ethyl acetate fractions in first three ratios were mixed and refractionated over silica column. Elution with benzene-chloroform (1:1, v/v) gave a white crystalline solid, m.p. 122-28°. Gc-ms analysis of the

substance (as trimethyl silyl ether derivatives) showed it to be a mixture of campesterol (1.07%, M^+ 472), stigmasterol (4.82%, M^+ 484), β -sitosterol (92.5%, M^+ 486), and an unidentified substance, the two-ion peaks 343, 386 are different from those of β -sitosterol.

Benzene-ethyl acetate (1 : 1) and ethyl acetate fractions were subjected to preparative layer chromatography on silica-gel using benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36 : 9 : 5) to yield BVI, BVII and BVIII, and two minor bands in order of increasing R_f values.

A mixture of BVI (100 mg), dimethyl sulphate, anhydrous potassium carbonate and dry acetone were refluxed together for 8 h. After the usual work up and purification over silica gel column it was crystallised from CHCl_3 -MeOH, m.p. 162-164°, (M^+ 622). It was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7', hexa-*O*-methyl[I-6, II-8]biflavone (agathisflavone) by nmr studies and comparison with those of the authentic sample⁴. The two minor bands were methylated to give the same methyl ether and were detected as mono- and di-*O*-methyl agathisflavone. The two fractions BVII and BVIII were characterised as quercetin and kaemferol, respectively by m.p., m.m.p. and co-tlc.

The acetone extract gave two bands which were characterised as betulinic acid and quercetin-3-glucoside (m.p. 221-24°). The identity was finally confirmed by direct comparison with authentic samples⁵.

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Platinum-Graphite Polarizable Electrode System for Non-aqueous Biamperometric Indication. Estimation of Mercaptans with Iodine

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RECENT adoption of the platinum-graphite combination for biamperometric indication involving aqueous and partially non-aqueous determinations¹⁻⁴ prompted to explore the condi-

tions suitable for its applicability in systems exclusively non-aqueous. The present communication reports an attempt to estimate small amounts of various mercaptans with iodine in a solution of *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Experimental

The experimental procedure with its circuit arrangement was essentially the same as employed earlier for aqueous determinations¹. A wax-impregnated graphite and a micro-platinum electrode suitably fixed in a rubber disc at a fixed interspace ~3 cm, constituted the electrode assembly between which was impressed a constant emf obtained from a battery-operated potentiometer, with graphite as positive.

All chemicals used were of the analytical grade except when stated otherwise. *N,N*-Dimethylformamide (E. Merck) prior to use was kept in contact with sodium carbonate for 48 h with occasional shaking and the decanted liquid was distilled for the fraction boiling between 148.5-149.5°. Test solutions of the given mercaptan (Fluka samples of *n*-butyl- and benzylmercaptans, 2-mercaptoethanol and thiophenol) as also of the titrant, iodine (B.D.H.) were prepared in the above solvent; these were standardised⁵ using copper(II) chloride for the mercaptans and sodium thiosulphate in aqueous medium for iodine.

A known amount of the mercaptan solution was taken in the titration vessel and the volume was adjusted to 30 ml, before addition of iodine from a semi-microburette. The cell current was measured (at a constant polarising emf varied in the range 100-350 mV) with a sensitive galvanometer after a lapse of usually 1 min following each addition. The solution was kept stirred throughout using a magnetic stirrer. Equivalence points were obtained from the corresponding current-volume plots. A set of representative results for the above substances is returned in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

As the present estimation is based on the oxidation of the mercaptan (according to the general scheme followed by Yoshimura and Miyamoto⁶, i.e. $2\text{DMF.R-SH} + \text{KI}_2 \rightarrow 2\text{DMF.R-S} + \text{KI} + 2\text{HI}$), presence of any unused iodine generates the current indicating couple I_3^-/I^- . This prevailing on completion of the process, introduces an abrupt onset of the cell current. The titration curves therefore, as anticipated, are found to be of the reversed L-shape with well defined breaks.

It is noted further that the polarising emf, requisite for obtaining reliable current magnitudes, is slightly greater than that required for similar work in an aqueous medium. However, it affects in no way either the general nature of the corresponding titration curves or the location of the end points; it enlarges simply the cell current.